

**FORENSIC AND PHARMACEUTICAL ANALYSIS
OF ADDICTIVE MORBIDITY BECAUSE OF THE
USE OF PSYCHOTROPIC PSYCHOACTIVE
SUBSTANCES IN UKRAINE
(RETROSPECTIVE ASPECT)**

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Introduction

The use of psychoactive substances is one of the leading factors in the deterioration of the mental health of the population. The dynamics of addictive morbidity in recent years is closely correlated with each other, as well as with other manifestations of social problems: the general mortality of the population; the number of suicides; the number of crimes committed, which in general affects the development of the country [1-5].

Earlier, in the framework of forensic and pharmaceutical studies, analyzed the indicators of addictive morbidity because of the use of drugs from the classification and legal group "narcotic drugs" (ICD-10

codes F11, F12, F14, F19) in Ukraine for the period of 2005–2008 years. In continuation of researches of addictive morbidity in Ukraine, retrospectively, studied the indicators of the use of psychoactive substances from the classification and legal group "psychotropic substances" [6-10].

Formulating the goals (tasks) of the article

The purpose of the work was to conduct a forensic and pharmaceutical analysis of indicators of addictive morbidity because of the use of psychoactive substances from the classification and legal group "psychotropic substances" in Ukraine in a retrospective aspect.

Presentation of the main research material (methods and objects) with the justification of the results

The *material* of the study was statistical data, scientific literature, regulatory documents, and Internet sources. In studying of the problem, used retrospective, documentary, normative and legal, forensic and pharmaceutical *methods* of analysis.

Results of the research and their discussion. Addictive morbidity refers to mental and behavioral disorders resulting from the use of psychoactive substances, which are classified in section F of the International Classification of Diseases of the 10th revision (ICD-10). The state takes a direct part in controlling of the circulation of psychoactive substances on the territory of Ukraine by developing and approving the legislative base [11-15].

Based on the analysis of regulatory documents in Table 1 shown the characteristics of psychoactive substances in accordance to ICD-10 codes and the corresponding classification and legal groups are given.

Table 1. Normative and legal characteristics of the psychoactive substances from the classification and legal group “psychotropic substances” by ICD-10 codes

ICD-10 code	Addiction morbidity type	Example of the psychoactive substance	Classification and legal group
F13	Because of the use of hypnotics and sedatives	Diazepam, phenobarbital	Psychotropic substances
F15	Because of the use of psychostimulants	Amphetamine	Psychotropic substances
F16	Because of the use of hallucinogens	LSD, psilocybin, mescaline	Psychotropic substances

From Table 1 it can be seen that the addictive morbidity due to the use of psychoactive substances from the classification and legal group "psychotropic substances" includes three ICD-10 codes: F13 – hypnotics and sedatives (diazepam, phenobarbital); F15 – psychostimulants (amphetamine); F16 – hallucinogens (LSD, psilocybin, and mescaline).

The conducted normative and legal analysis of the current legislation testifies that the indicated in Table 1 psychoactive substances refer to psychotropic substances,

the circulation of which is limited (Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine No. 770 from May 06, 2000 "On approval of the list of narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances and precursors").

Analysis of the indicators of the registered addictive morbidity because of the use of sleeping pills and sedatives (F13) in Ukraine for the period of 2005–2008 (Fig. 1) characterizes the relative stability of this indicator in 2008 compared to 2005.

Figure 1. Registered addictive morbidity because of the use of hypnotics and sedatives substances (F13) in Ukraine for 2005–2008 (per 100 thousand population)

Analysis of the registered addictive morbidity because of the use of psychostimulants (F15) in Ukraine

for the period of 2005–2008 (Fig. 2) indicates its decrease by 24% in 2008 compared with 2005.

Figure 2. Registered addictive morbidity because of the use of psychostimulants (F15) in Ukraine for 2005–2008 (per 100 thousand population)

Analysis of the indicators of the registered addictive morbidity because of the use of hallucinogens (F16) in

Ukraine for the period of 2005–2008 (Fig. 3) indicates its stable indicator in 2008 compared with 2005.

Figure 3. Registered addictive morbidity because of the use of hallucinogens (F16) in Ukraine for 2005-2008 (per 100 thousand population)

Thus, carried out forensic and pharmaceutical analysis of addictive morbidity because of the use of

psychotropic psychoactive substances in Ukraine in a retrospective aspect.

Conclusions from the conducted research and prospects of further development of this direction

Established, that psychoactive substances from the classification and legal group "psychotropic substances" refer to substances whose circulation is limited at the legislative level. The results of the analysis of the registered addictive morbidity in Ukraine for the period of 2005–2008 because of the use of psychotropic psychoactive substances testify the following. Stability of the index of addictive morbidity because of the use of hypnotic and sedative substances (F13) and hallucinogens (F16) in 2008 in comparison with 2005; about a 24% reduction in the addictive morbidity because of the use of psychostimulants (F15) in 2008 compared with 2005.

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Shapovalov V.V. (jr.), Gudzenko A. A., Zbrozhek S. I., Negretskiy S.N., Shapovalova V.A., Shapovalov V.V.

Introduction. The use of psychoactive substances is one of the leading factors in the deterioration of the mental health of the population. The dynamics of addictive morbidity in recent years is closely correlated with each other, as well as with other manifestations of social problems: the general mortality of the population; the number of suicides; the number of crimes committed, which in general affects the development of the country. **Materials and methods.** The material of the study was statistical data, scientific literature, regulatory documents, and Internet sources. In studying of the problem, used retrospective, documentary, normative and legal, forensic and pharmaceutical methods of analysis.

Results and discussion. The article presents the results of the forensic and pharmaceutical analysis of the addictive morbidity in Ukraine for the period of 2005–2008 based on example of psychotropic psychoactive substances. Distinguished three codes of the International Classification of Diseases of the 10th revision, which correspond to the addictive morbidity due to the use of

psychotropic substances: F13 – hypnotics and sedatives (diazepam, phenobarbital); F15 – psychostimulants (amphetamine); F16 – hallucinogens (LSD, psilocybin, mescaline). Given the indicators of the listed types of addictive morbidity in Ukraine (per 100 thousand population) in a retrospective aspect. **Conclusions.** Established, that psychoactive substances from the classification and legal group "psychotropic substances" refer to substances whose circulation is limited at the legislative level. The results of the analysis of the registered addictive morbidity in Ukraine for the period of 2005–2008 because of the use of psychotropic psychoactive substances testify the following. Stability of the index of addictive morbidity because of the use of hypnotic and sedative substances (F13) and hallucinogens (F16) in 2008 in comparison with 2005; about a 24% reduction in the addictive morbidity because of the use of psychostimulants (F15) in 2008 compared with 2005. **Keywords:** forensic pharmacy, psychoactive substances, addictive morbidity, classification and legal groups, psychotropic substances.